

PERFORMING AND NON-PERFORMING LEARNERS IN MATHEMATICS 8: A DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS

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Performing and Non-Performing Learners in Mathematics 8: A Discriminant Analysis

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the factors affecting the academic achievement of Grade 8 students. Specifically, it sought to determine if there is a significant relationship between academic performance in Mathematics and each of the following constructs: IQ, academic performance in Science, academic performance in English, and frequency of online gaming. The scores used to determine the performing and non-performing were taken from the year-end test results of the Division Integration on Assessment of Learning Monitoring and Evaluation (DIAL-ME) conducted by the division of Cebu province last school year 2022-2023. The study was composed of 80 students, the upper 40 for performing, and the lower 40 for non-performing after their scores were ranked from highest to lowest. There were 183 grade 8 students from San Agustin National High School, San Agustin Madridejos, Cebu. The grades of the students in Science 8 and English 8 were obtained in the school records as a basis for academic performance. The Intelligence Quotient (IQ) of the students was measured using commercial IQ tests taken from <https://new-iq-test.com/#sts> and for the frequency of gaming, the research questionnaire was taken from the website Gaming Addicts Anonymous (n.d). By examining the 4 constructs, it sought to determine how they influenced learners' success or struggle in mathematics. The study utilized a quantitative descriptive-comparative research design, analyzing the mathematical abilities of both high and low-performing students concerning these factors, particularly in the areas of IQ and academic performance, while online gaming was found to have a moderate negative impact on the mathematical proficiency of non-performing students. The findings offer insights that can guide the development of intervention strategies to enhance learners' performance in mathematics and address the potential effects of online gaming.

Keywords: *mathematical ability, academic performance, discriminant analysis, grade 8 students, mathematics*

Introduction

Mathematics is a vital subject in elementary and secondary schools that teaches learners the essential information and life-organizing abilities they need (Ariyanti & Santoso, 2020). It is important to teach learners the basic teachings and fundamentals of mathematics, as these will be crucial to learners as they progress to higher mathematics and with application to their lives.

Mathematical ability is operating, evaluating, and comprehending mathematical ideas, patterns, and numbers. Strong mathematical thinkers can apply their knowledge to real-world problems, think critically, and quickly pick new ideas. As mathematical ability is closely dependent on cognitive functions, logical reasoning, and numerical processing, it is essential to compare the factors affecting the performance of San Agustin National High School learners who perform or do not perform well in mathematics 8 related to the four constructs: IQ level, academic performance in Science, academic performance in English, and frequency level of online gaming in enhancing their cognitive domain.

In the Philippines, the mathematical abilities of learners are poor. Based on the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), Filipino learners were among the lowest-performing groups in all the participating countries (Bernardo et. al, 2022). The reasons Filipinos believe mathematics to be a challenging subject may have to do with how learners view the topic or the methods they use to learn the subject which impacts their academic achievement (Abalde & Oco, 2023). Learners will never understand mathematics until they try to engage themselves in it. According to Gafoor and Kurukkan 2015, learners' lack of prior knowledge is the main factor contributing to their difficulty with mathematics, and they believed that this was due to their quick forgetting of previously learned content. In the local setting, at San Agustin National High School, it is observed that many learners display poor performance in mathematical computations, understanding the fundamentals of mathematics such as fractions, integers, and problem-solving, specifically in algebra subjects. They need educational assistance and guidance on the basic principles of mathematics and have problems with the correct answers. Moreover, they also have difficulty understanding and analyzing mathematical sentences and problem-solving. It was noticed that many learners who struggled with mathematics were actively engaged in online games. This observation led to exploring and comparing the learners' mathematical abilities to factors like academic performance, IQs, and the frequency of online gaming.

This study determined the factors influencing the academic achievement of Grade 8 students in mathematics by exploring four key constructs: IQ, academic performance in science and English, and the frequency of online gaming. The sample included 80 students selected from a larger group of 183 Grade 8 students from San Agustin National High School in Madridejos, Cebu, based on their year-end test results from the Division Integration on Assessment of Learning Monitoring and Evaluation (DIAL-ME) for the school year 2022-2023. The top 40 students were categorized as performing, while the bottom 40 were classified as non-performing. The students' science and English grades were obtained from school records, while their IQ was assessed using a commercial test from a website

(new-iq-test.com). The frequency of online gaming was measured using a questionnaire sourced from Gaming Addicts Anonymous. The study employed a quantitative descriptive-comparative research design to analyze the differences between performing and non-performing students, with a particular focus on IQ, academic performance in science and English, and the frequency of online gaming. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was set for all statistical tests to determine the relevance of the findings.

The findings highlighted a potential cross-subject influence where their difficulties in one subject, such as math, may be associated with or even contributed to challenges in another subject, like English. This suggested that these non-performing students might have broader academic challenges that impacted multiple areas. A moderate negative correlation was also found between online gaming frequency and mathematical ability, particularly among non-performing students. The findings provided valuable insights for educators to develop targeted intervention strategies to improve math performance and mitigate the negative effects of excessive online gaming.

The study offers useful insights for parents regarding the factors that influence their children's academic performance in mathematics. By understanding the roles that IQ, academic performance in science and English, and online gaming habits play, parents can make more informed decisions about supporting their children's education. They can help encourage better time management, foster a positive learning environment, and set boundaries on gaming to ensure a balance between recreational activities and academic responsibilities. It is also significant to the teacher since it gives vital information on the academic variables that influence learners' progress in mathematics, enabling them to determine which students might require more assistance. Teachers can use the results to help them create focused intervention plans for learners with different skill levels. Additionally, understanding how performance in disciplines like science and English relates to mathematics can result in integrated teaching strategies that improve overall academic achievement. Students are encouraged to consider their academic practices, particularly how they balance their schoolwork with leisure pursuits. Furthermore, realizing how their performance in mathematics relates to their success in other topics, like science and English, might inspire students to pursue excellence in all subject areas since they realize that mastery of one subject can improve performance in another.

Research Questions

This study sought to compare the mathematical ability level of performing and non-performing Grade eight students in San Agustin National High School, Cebu Province division, for the school year 2022-2023 as a basis for developing a strategic plan. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following:

1. What is the level of mathematical ability of Grade eight learners when classified as performing and non-performing?
2. What is the learners' level of performance of the following constructs?
 - 2.1. IQ level;
 - 2.2. academic performance in english;
 - 2.3. academic performance in science; and
 - 2.4. online gaming?
3. Is there a significant difference between the performing and non-performing students in the four constructs?
4. What factors discriminate against the performing and non-performing students in Mathematics 8?
5. What strategic intervention plan can be developed based on the result of the study?

Literature Review

Collaboration Between English and Mathematics

The collaboration between English and Mathematics is ideal, as mathematics fosters discipline, enhances cognitive thinking, and encourages logical and creative thinking. At the same time, English is equipped with the communication skills necessary to articulate the complexities of mathematics to a broader audience (Priveswari & Rintaningrum, 2021). In a study conducted by Leshem and Markovits (2013), the possibility of collaboration between English and Mathematics instructors is a thought-provoking concept that opens the door for additional inquiry and exploration in the field of education. In addition, understanding how personal experiences and perceptions impact views on teaching and learning is critical for enhancing educational practices and encouraging successful pedagogy in both areas. The concurrent routes of English and mathematics carry the potential to develop well-rounded persons who are skilled at both problem-solving and good communication, in addition to enhancing academic success.

Mathematical Achievement and English Proficiency

The relationship between mathematical achievement and English proficiency is crucial, particularly among students who are still learning English, according to Henry et al. The results of Umayam et al. (2016) suggest that English content comprises 30% and therefore has more effect on math scores among English Language Learners (ELL) than other groups, although the factor is reduced to effectively account for socio-economic difference in race adjustment as proposed by Card & Krueger (1992). While mathematics is considered somewhat a universal language, you still need to be able to have some understanding of the language if you are going to understand the problems, instructions, and terminology used.

Therefore, students with stronger English skills tend to do better in math. There is a positive correlation between the ability to succeed

in math and being proficient in English. Yet, this relationship may be different at the various grade levels. In this way, older students could see modest gains in English proficiency but still perform poorly in math, indicating that the higher level of mathematical content might exceed lagging language skills. Also, studies have proved that the past results of students, on the one hand, can massively influence their academic performance on the other, e.g., prior mathematics/English achievement is predictive for future English/Mathematics scores (Roslan & Chen). English proficiency corresponds with better educational achievement in subjects such as mathematics (Olanipekun & Ishola 2014).

The Role of Science in Mathematical Performance

A well-rounded curriculum must include instruction in math and science, especially in the 21st century when these topics are crucial for the development of skills for future reference. Al-Mutawah (n.d.) highlighted the relevance of non-cognitive characteristics, such as grit and attitude, in predicting student progress in mathematics and science. He stated that the link between these factors and academic achievement is favorable, emphasizing the necessity for educators and curriculum designers to modify their teaching strategies and resources to increase students' enthusiasm and involvement. The education industry can work toward better results and encourage greater interest in these important areas by recognizing the importance of non-cognitive variables, ultimately giving students the skills they need in the 21st century. Studying math and science would promote analytical and evaluative skills, scientific reasoning, and the capacity to solve quantifiable problems (Guruathomeforyou, 2023). Hakim (2023) demonstrated in his study that both subjects' science and mathematics are significantly related to students' overall performance. Based on research conducted at East Teluk Jame 1 Public Middle School involving 227 students, it appears that those who were great in mathematics also had outstanding performances in science, and vice versa. This association was calculated using the Spearman correlation test, and this approach showed a coefficient of 0.479 ($P < 0.001$) indicating that both subjects have a moderate to strong relationship. Mathematics is more abstract; science emphasizes hands-on research methods although Hakim (2023) underscored that both share essential educational aspirations like critical thinking and problem-solving-based activity as well as the application of concepts to practical situations.

Cognitive Abilities and Mathematical Performance

A study conducted by Hendriyanto (2022). The objective was to examine if any correlation exists between IQ levels among the students and their math achievements. The research established that mathematics achievement invested 16% of the total variance in IQ scores with a correlation value of 0.4. This moderate positive correlation shows that while mathematics achievement had a relation to IQ, there are probably more factors that cause differences in IQ levels. This establishes the extent to which mathematics achievement correlates highly with IQ. The fact that cognitive abilities and academic performance go hand in hand is illustrated in this. Higher studies together with higher IQs tend to correlate with higher mathematics learning achievement levels because high-IQ students are more likely to understand and solve problems compared to low-IQ students (Andari & Lestari 2023).

The Influence of Online Gaming on Academic Performance

According to Penaso and Gaylo (2019), the amount of time spent on interactive games did not significantly affect students' mathematical performance, suggesting that other underlying factors may play a more critical role. This highlights the need for a more nuanced understanding of how online gaming interacts with cognitive development and academic skills. Further insights were provided by Austria et al. (2022), who argued that the integration of technology in education has transformed the learning landscape. Their research emphasizes the potential for online platforms to enhance student engagement and provide personalized feedback. This suggests that, when used appropriately, online gaming can foster skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving, which are essential for success in mathematics.

Discriminating Factors in Mathematics Performance

Several factors have been identified in the literature as influencing students' performance in mathematics. These include cognitive abilities such as IQ, academic performance in related subjects like English and Science, and extracurricular activities, particularly online gaming. Research suggests that students' performance in mathematics is not solely determined by their abilities in the subject itself but is also influenced by broader academic skills and personal habits. For instance, studies have shown a positive correlation between higher IQ levels and improved mathematical performance (Hendriyanto, 2022; Hakim, 2023). Similarly, strong performance in Science and English has been found to support mathematical success, as these subjects develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills that are transferable to mathematics. Online gaming, while fostering certain cognitive abilities, can also lead to distraction, negatively affecting students' academic focus. These various factors contribute to the disparity in mathematical performance, making it essential to identify and understand the specific factors that discriminate between performing and non-performing students in mathematics. This study aims to explore these factors at San Agustin National High School to better understand the underlying causes of students' success or struggles in Mathematics 8.

Methodology

Research Design

A research design provides the structure and strategy for investigating the research problem. This study employed a quantitative

descriptive-discriminant analysis, systematically examining how variables such as IQ, academic performance, and online gaming frequency differentiated performing and non-performing learners in Mathematics 8. This study employed a quantitative descriptive-discriminant analysis to compare the factors influencing the mathematical performance of Grade Eight learners with the four constructs: the IQ level, the academic performance in English, the academic performance in Science, and the frequency level of online gaming. This design facilitates a systematic examination of differences between performing and non-performing students in mathematics, enabling the assessment of variables such as intelligence quotient (IQ), academic performance in Science and English, and online gaming frequency.

Performing and non-performing groups were classified based on the (DIAL ME) Division Integration on Assessment of Learning, Monitoring, and Evaluation result in Mathematics Eight. Questionnaires were used to identify how frequently students played online games. The grades in English eight and Science eight were used to identify the academic performance of the students, and the learners then took an IQ test to determine whether learners who performed better in math excelled in academic performance and had high IQs or whether the non-performing learners in Math eight had performed better in academic subjects and higher IQ than that of non-online gamers or vice versa.

Respondents

Respondents are individuals who participate in a study, providing valuable data to address the research objectives. The study was conducted at San Agustin National High School, focusing on Grade 8 students. The total population comprises 183 students, from which a purposive sample of 80 was selected. The 80 respondents, selected from a larger group of 183 students, were categorized based on their year-end Mathematics scores, ensuring a focused comparison between performing and non-performing learners. This sample size consisted of 40 performing students, identified by their high scores on the Division Integration on Assessment of Learning Monitoring and Evaluation (DIAL-ME), an offline year-end assessment conducted by the division office for the school year 2022-2023 in Mathematics subject, and 40 non-performing students with low scores. Participants were classified based on their scores in mathematics to ensure a clear distinction between the two groups.

Instrument

Data collection involved several instruments and was conducted in a structured manner. The primary tool used to measure students' mathematical performance was the DIAL-ME test, which provided year-end standardized assessment results reflecting their abilities. The scores of 183 students were ranked from highest to lowest, and the top 40 were identified as the performing while the bottom 40 were classified as the non-performing students in math. Additionally, students' academic grades in science and English were obtained from school records to evaluate their overall academic performance. To assess cognitive abilities, standardized IQ tests taken from <https://new-iq-test.com/#sts> were administered to participants. The frequency of online gaming among students was evaluated using a structured questionnaire adapted from Gaming Addicts Anonymous. This questionnaire included items on the frequency and types of online games played, capturing essential information regarding their gaming behaviors. The survey is conducted with a limited number of 80 students, regardless of gender. Paper pens were used throughout the data collection. Participating students gave their explicit consent to abide by the Data Privacy Act. Any release of student information had to adhere closely to confidentiality. The front page of the questionnaire includes a clear statement about the study's goals and conditions. Before proceeding with the questionnaire, the students had to consciously check a box to indicate their agreement with these terms.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedure outlines the sequential steps taken to collect data while ensuring accuracy and adherence to ethical standards. After obtaining the necessary permissions, academic records were reviewed, IQ tests were administered, and gaming questionnaires were distributed. The process was conducted systematically, ensuring clarity and fairness to all participants. The data collection process was divided into three sections.

To conduct the study, the researcher first sought consent from the school administration. They then filed a written request to the district supervisor and a letter to the Division Superintendent with their endorsement. After the superintendent gave his consent, a letter was written to the principal of the school where the study was conducted. During the actual gathering, data was gathered from the school's guidance designate as a consequence of Mathematics Eight in the DIAL-ME. After identifying the performing and non-performing students, the identified students' English eight and Science eight grades for the school year 2022-2023 were collected to determine their academic performance. It was followed by the administration of intelligence tests. The students were gathered in a room. Efforts were made to ensure that they understood the study's goal and their rights as participants. Questionnaires were distributed to determine the frequency with which they played online games. Students were given adequate time to complete the questionnaire, which included a consent letter, general instructions, and actual questions. Responses are automatically collected as soon as they are completed. It was held after their class hours.

Finally, in the post-data gathering, the gathered questionnaires were properly disposed of in accordance with ethical norms, data security, participant privacy, and research integrity. All paper surveys were shredded and burned, and all digital copies of the data were erased from computers. All ethical rules were observed for data disposal.

Data Analysis

Quantitative analysis was employed to compare the performance of performing and non-performing students across the variables of interest. A t-test for independent samples was utilized to assess the significance of differences in mean scores between the two groups concerning their IQ, academic performance in Science and English, and online gaming frequency. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was set for all statistical tests to determine the relevance of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. It has been approved following the protocol of the Research and Ethics Committee of the University of the Visayas with Reference No. NP2024EDD-056 dated March 12, 2024. The research involved grade 8 students participating voluntarily in the survey. Before completion of the questionnaires, an accompanying cover letter explained the confidentiality and purpose of the study, the potential objectives, and the voluntary participation. No financial incentives were provided for participating in the study. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Furthermore, by adhering to these ethical principles, this research contributed meaningfully to the understanding of the four constructs' impact on mathematical performance in educational settings. As a token of appreciation for their voluntary participation, students received snacks during the data collection process. This small gesture enhanced their experience while recognizing their contributions to the research.

Results and Discussion

Through examining the mathematical skills and the understanding demonstrated by each group of learners, the researcher identified key differences in their capabilities. The grade 8 learners classified as “performing” demonstrated significantly higher mean mathematical abilities scores compared to the “non-performing” group.

Students' Mathematical Ability

The data shows a significant difference between the mathematical abilities of performing and non-performing students. The mean score for performing students is 19.95, while the mean score for non-performing students is 7.92. This indicates a substantial difference in average performance between the two groups.

In the Standard Deviations, this suggests that the scores of performing students are more widespread than those of non-performing students. The computed t-value is 25.96, with a p-value of 0.000. This highly significant result (p -value < 0.05) implies that the observed difference in means is unlikely to be due to chance.

Table 1. *Level of Mathematical Ability classified as Performing and Non-Performing Students*

<i>Students</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
Performing	19.95	2.83
Non-Performing	7.92	.73

This table compares students' performance in English across different levels of Mathematics achievement, categorizing them as either “performing” or “non-performing.” Performing students have outstanding levels with a mean score of 90.42, while non-performing students have satisfactory English performance with a mean score of 84.80. The non-performing students have difficulty in mathematics more than in English. Understanding why a significant number of students in the “Very Satisfactory” and “Satisfactory” categories were non-performing in mathematics could lead to insights into issues like teaching methods, curriculum challenges, or student engagement. In a study conducted by Archarya (2017), he found that one of the reasons why students find Mathematics challenging is because there is mathematical anxiety, disinterest, or a bad feeling about the subject.

Students' Performance in the Four Constructs

Meanwhile, the performing students have higher performance in science, as many are in the outstanding group with a mean of 91.08. On the other hand, the non-performing group has satisfactory and very satisfactory performance in science with a mean score of 86.55, contrary to their Mathematics performance. Their better performance in science than in mathematics could be due to their way of teaching, which is project-based. This is supported by the study conducted by Hindun et al., which states that the students' Science literacy is improved by using project-based learning.

For the IQ test results, it is found that the performing students in math have also higher IQs with a mean of 81.55 which is leveled as borderline mental disability, compared to the non-performing students in math with a mean score of 67.93, described as mild mental disability.

As for the video game involvement of students, it is also found that most performing students are not really into video gaming, as shown in the result, performing students are classified as low. On the other hand, non-performing students are classified as moderate. This suggests that non-performing students are moderately engaged in.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Students' Performance in the Four Constructs

Constructs	Level	Performing Students		Non-Performing Students	
		F	%	F	%
English	Outstanding	22	55	0	0
	Very Satisfactory	15	37.5	23	57.5
	Satisfactory	3	7.5	17	42.5
	Mean		90.43		84.80
Science	Descriptive Rating		Outstanding		Satisfactory
	Outstanding	28	70	0	0
	Very Satisfactory	11	27.5	39	97.5
	Satisfactory	1	2.5	1	2.5
IQ	Mean		91.08		86.55
	Descriptive Rating		Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	
	115-120 Above Average	2	5	0	0
	85 – 114 Average intelligence	17	42.5	0	0
Video Games	70 - 84	12	30	25	62.5
	Borderline mental disability	3	7.5	10	25
	55 – 69 Mild mental disability	6	15	5	12.5
	40-54 Moderate mental disability		81.55		67.83
Video Games	Mean		81.55		67.83
	Descriptive Rating		Borderline mental disability		Mild mental disability
	High	1	2.5	4	10
	Moderate	12	30	24	60
Video Games	Low	27	67.5	12	30
	Mean		5.15		8.68
	Descriptive Rating		Low		Moderate

As for the video game involvement of students, it is also found that most performing students are not really into video gaming, as shown in the result, performing students are classified as low. On the other hand, non-performing students are classified as moderate. This suggests that non-performing students are moderately engaged in playing video games than the performing students in math. In a study conducted by Chi Ani et al. (2023), students themselves admitted playing online games does affect their academic performance.

Difference of Students' Performance in the Four Constructs

The data table shows the mean, standard deviation, computed t-value, and p-value for students' performance in different constructs (English, Science, IQ, and video games) categorized into performing and non-performing groups.

Table 3. Difference in Students' Performance in the Four Constructs

Constructs	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	Computed t	p-value	Remarks
English	Performing	90.43	4.19	7.19	0	Significant
	Non-performing	84.80	2.63			
Science	Performing	91.08	3.30	7.73	0	Significant
	Non-performing	86.55	1.68			
IQ	Performing	81.55	22.75	3.35	0.001	Significant
	Non-performing	67.83	12.37			
Video games	Performing	5.15	3.59	4.01	.000	Significant
	Non-performing	8.68	4.24			

Note: Level of significance = .05; Performing n=40; Non-Performing n=40

It was hypothesized that the four constructs do not differ between the performing and non-performing students in Mathematics. To test the hypothesis, the t-test of the independent sample was applied. Table 3 shows the comparative analysis of the means of the two groups.

In English performance, the t-value of 7.185 indicates a very strong difference between the English performance of non-performing and performing students in math. The p-value of .000 (typically reported as $p < .001$) confirms that this difference is statistically significant, meaning the likelihood that this result is due to chance is extremely low. These results suggest a significant link between performance in math and English. Specifically, students who are non-performing in math also tend to have significantly lower performance in English.

The findings highlight a potential cross-subject influence where difficulties in one subject, such as math, may be associated with or even contribute to challenges in another subject, like English. This suggests that these non-performing students might have broader academic challenges that impact multiple areas.

All the results were statistically significant; the difference between the “performing” and the “non-performing” groups is not due to random chance. The p-values for all the variables are extremely low. (English 0, Science 0, IQ 0.001, and Video games.000). This means the probability of obtaining such a large difference between the means if there is no real difference. There is strong evidence that exists between the groups in a population.

The Discriminant Analysis Matrix

Table 4 presents the factors or constructs that discriminate between the performing and non-performing students in Mathematics. The overall Wilks Lambda of .095 is quite close to 0, indicating a strong difference between the performing and non-performing groups on the combined five dependent variables. This value suggests that the groups have significantly different mean vectors, meaning that the independent variables (groupings) have a strong effect on the mathematics performance of the students.

Since the Wilks' Lambda is described as "significant," it means that the p-value associated with this statistic is less than the typical alpha level (e.g., .05). This reinforces the conclusion that the differences between the groups are statistically significant. The significant Wilks' Lambda indicates that there are substantial differences between the groups being compared in the study. These differences are evident when considering the multiple dependent variables together, implying that the groups have distinct characteristics, behaviors, or outcomes based on the independent variable(s) being tested. rather than individually. This could imply that the groups have similar characteristics, behaviors, or outcomes based on the independent variable(s) being tested. The significance of Wilks' Lambda indicates meaningful differences among the groups.

Table 4. *Discriminant Analysis Matrix Between Performing and Non-Performing Students in Mathematics*

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Overall Wilks Lambda</i>	<i>Chi-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>
English	.602	51.622	.000	.095	177.385	.000
Science	.566	59.741	.000			
IQ	.874	11.239	.001			
Video Games	.829	16.101	.000			

Since the Wilks' Lambda is described as "significant," it means that the p-value associated with this statistic is less than the typical alpha level (e.g., .05). This reinforces the conclusion that the differences between the groups are statistically significant. The significant Wilks' Lambda indicates that there are substantial differences between the groups being compared in the study. These differences are evident when considering the multiple dependent variables together, implying that the groups have distinct characteristics, behaviors, or outcomes based on the independent variable(s) being tested. rather than individually. This could imply that the groups have similar characteristics, behaviors, or outcomes based on the independent variable(s) being tested. The significance of Wilks' Lambda indicates meaningful differences among the groups.

The independent variable(s) used to categorize the groups IQ, English performance, Science performance, IQ, video games, and Division Integration Assessment on Learning, Monitoring, and Evaluation are likely effective in producing different outcomes across the dependent variables. Given the significance of Wilks' Lambda, further post-hoc analyses (like pairwise comparisons or discriminant function analysis) may be warranted to understand specifically which dependent variables contribute most to the differences between the groups. It's also important to explore the practical significance and the effect sizes associated with these differences to understand the real-world implications of the findings. The study's findings could inform decisions or actions, such as tailoring interventions to different groups or focusing on specific variables that contribute most to the observed differences.

The table also shows the individual contribution of each independent variable to the mathematics performance of the students. All the constructs were significant, meaning they have significant contributions to the mathematics performance. The p-values were less than .05, suggesting that the hypothesis of no significant difference between the performing and non-performing groups was rejected. It means that the combined mean of the four constructs of the performing group is significantly different from the combined mean of the performing group.

Of the four constructs, it is only in video games where the non-performing group is higher than the performing group. This suggests that video games have a higher probability of hindering students' performance, especially in Mathematics.

Conclusions

Mathematics performance is dependent on other constructs such as language (English), analytical skills (Science), and study habits (video games). The innate cognitive capability of an individual is an attribute of mathematics performance.

Performing grade eight students in San Agustin National High School have higher mathematical ability and have higher mean scores in all constructs than non-performing students but in video games. It's interesting to observe that non-performing students play video games more than performing ones do. There are notable distinctions between the performing and non-performing groups when comparing the mean scores of the four constructs, except the video game variable. These variations suggest that the data exhibits unique patterns that set the two groups apart in terms of academic achievement.

Additionally, the discriminant analysis highlights that when assessing students' ability in mathematics, the aggregate mean of the four constructs—aside from video games—acts as a distinguishing factor. This indicates that differentiating between students who perform well and those who do not in mathematics can be accomplished with a comprehensive method that considers variables like IQ, Science, and English grades. All four constructs are discriminating factors in the mathematics performance of the students. Overall, the results show significant differences in performance between performing and non-performing students across all constructs analyzed, indicating that students classified as performing generally achieve higher scores in Division Integration Assessment and likewise good grades in English, Science, and IQ tests, while low scores in video gaming, contrary to the non-performing students.

These findings directly address the main problem of the study, namely, the identification of important factors that distinguish performing and non-performing Grade 8 students in mathematics. Having looked at variables such as IQ, academic performance in both English and science, as well as gaming frequency, the study could isolate areas that influence performance in mathematics. The results support the hypothesis that students with stronger abilities in related academic areas and higher cognitive abilities perform better in mathematics. These relationships underscore the interconnected nature of academic skills, suggesting that improvements in one area, such as language or analytical skills, could potentially boost performance in mathematics as well. This insight, therefore, points towards the necessity for integrated approaches to learning that reinforce cross-disciplinary skills, hence supporting the holistic academic development of the students.

High gaming frequency, in its turn, showed a negative association with performance, with discriminant analysis further confirming the hypothesis that each of the four constructs represents an important predictor of mathematics performance. This evidence illustrates the roles of learning habits and mind engagement in achievement, and it's specifically in math, where constant practice, hard work, and strong studying are the keys to perfect skills. It will make educators build interventions focused not only on mathematical skills but also that promote good study habits and a better balance of outside activities as well as supporting the English and Science streams. The next step will be to push forward studies on this framework with further factors or tests on intervention effectiveness, all leading towards the improvement of mathematics achievement through a holistic and supportive education strategy.

The following are recommended:

The school may offer specialized programs or interventions designed to improve student's math skills and monitor progress during the implementation. It may be carried out to see the effects of the infusion of concepts in English and Science in teaching mathematics.

The school head may consider intensifying peer tutoring initiatives within the classroom to provide learners with supplementary support to improve their math skills. Teachers may involve students and parents in promoting balanced digital use, especially in gaming. They may conduct workshops or class sessions that would educate students about the effects of over-gaming on academic performance and encourage self-regulation as part of their larger academic responsibility.

Mathematics teachers should embrace interdisciplinary teaching methods where math, language arts, and science are interconnected. This may include instruction that focuses on reading comprehension in solving math problems or that uses scientific examples when applying math concepts. This would help the students see connections between the subjects and therefore perform better in math and other related subjects.

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